

Milestones for Emergency Psychiatry Fellowship

PC1—Evaluation and diagnosis of the patient				
<p>A. Thorough evaluation of the patient presenting with a psychiatric emergency, including interviewing, integrating multiple data sources (including collateral gathering and use), and using evidence-based assessment tools</p> <p>B. Determine and ensure appropriate monitoring, implementing risk mitigation strategies in the emergency environment</p> <p>C. Assess suicide, violence, and medical risk in patients with undifferentiated presentations</p>				
Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Level 4	Level 5
<p>1.1/ABC Provides basic psychiatric assessment and treatment recommendations, requiring indirect supervision with direct supervision available</p> <p>1.2/B Determines appropriate level of monitoring in an emergency environment</p> <p>1.3/C Screens for patient safety, including suicidal and homicidal ideation using evidence-based tools</p> <p>1.4/ABC Appropriately determines the need for acute hospitalization</p>	<p>2.1/AC Integrates multiple sources of information in developing an assessment</p> <p>2.2/ABC Manages emergent presentations of more complex patients under indirect supervision with direct supervision available</p> <p>2.3/AC Acquires efficient, accurate and relevant history customized to the current chief complaint</p> <p>2.4/BC Efficiently synthesizes information into a concise and comprehensive formulation</p>	<p>3.1/AC Applies standardized assessment tools and evidence-based practice models in planning treatment</p> <p>3.2/AB Collaborates with multiple providers in a multidisciplinary care approach on challenging patient presentations</p> <p>3.3/AC Identifies and investigates important pathology incidental to the initial visit, including acute medical concerns</p>	<p>4.1/ABC Independently evaluates and manages complicated and challenging patient presentations including through collaboration with external clinical partners</p> <p>4.2/AB Able to incorporate an understanding of community-based, social and complex systems of care issues into treatment planning</p>	<p>5.1/ABC Leads a high functioning, efficient, multidisciplinary emergency service</p> <p>5.2/ABC Supervises and serves as a role model for trainees and staff</p>

Supplementary File 1

PC2—Emergent treatment of psychiatric symptoms				
<p>A. Utilize brief psychotherapy to treat patients in crisis, including with the use of verbal de-escalation and psychoeducation</p> <p>B. Prescribe medication to treat agitation, withdrawal, and other emergency conditions</p> <p>C. Triage and stabilize medical co-morbidities in patients with acute behavioral health presentations</p> <p>D. Direct a multidisciplinary team in safely managing scenarios with high risk of injury</p>				
Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Level 4	Level 5
<p>1.1/ACD Identifies indications and opportunities for proactive treatment of psychiatric emergencies (eg, early verbal de-escalation)</p> <p>1.2/BC Distinguish and manage life-threatening conditions associated with psychiatric symptoms (eg, delirium, alcohol withdrawal)</p>	<p>2.1/ACD Provides trauma-informed and effective verbal de-escalation for agitated patients</p> <p>2.2/BC Initiates treatment planning for emergent presentations with minimal supervision</p> <p>2.3/D Coordinates a team response to emergent psychiatric presentations requiring indirect supervision with direct supervision available</p>	<p>3.1/A Delivers brief psychotherapy to patients and families in crisis</p> <p>3.2/BCD Applies evidence-based algorithms in initiating treatment of agitation</p> <p>3.3/BCD Identifies and manages existing and emerging medical symptoms</p> <p>3.4/ABCD Appropriately modifies treatment approach and flexibly applies practice guidelines to fit patient needs</p>	<p>4.1/ABC Diagnoses and manages uncommon presentations of rare psychiatric emergencies</p> <p>4.2/BD Leads a team in managing high-risk patient scenarios (eg, developing individualized care plans, leading a critical incident review)</p>	<p>5.1/ABCD Supervises and serves as a role model for trainees and staff</p> <p>5.2/ABCD Discovers novel approaches and evidence for treating psychiatric emergencies</p>

Supplementary File 1

PC3—Treatment planning to improve patient care in the hospital and after discharge				
<p>A. Initiate pharmacologic treatment to enhance outcomes, maintain safety, and begin symptom management</p> <p>B. Connect the patient to the least restrictive level of appropriate care</p> <p>C. Deliver evidence-based interventions to enhance outcomes after emergency department discharge, including reducing the risk of self-harm and suicide</p>				
Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Level 4	Level 5
<p>1.1/AC Recognizes opportunities to enhance discharging patients’ outcomes</p> <p>1.2/B Identifies appropriate alternatives to hospitalization and initiates referral to those resources</p> <p>1.3/AC Appropriately educates patients and provides for appropriate ongoing monitoring of pharmacologic interventions</p> <p>1.4/ABC Seeks consultation appropriately to enhance outcomes/care</p>	<p>2.1/AC Integrates evidence-based strategies for reducing suicide and violence after ED discharge requiring indirect supervision with direct supervision available</p> <p>2.2/ABC Manages straightforward emergency psychiatric presentations with minimal supervision</p> <p>2.3/BC Involves community supports and resources in discharge planning</p>	<p>3.1/ABC Develops treatment plans through collaboration with a multidisciplinary team including midlevel providers</p> <p>3.2/BC Applies standardized screening and assessment tools to facilitate transitions of care from the ED</p> <p>3.3/ABC Develops treatment plans that reflect the patient’s financial and cultural circumstances</p>	<p>4.1/ABC Develops treatment plans for complex and high-risk patient presentations that incorporate community partners, cultural preferences and barriers, and evidence-based interventions</p> <p>4.2/B Manages conflicts among multiple services in instances of challenging patient dispositions</p>	<p>5.1/ABC Develops multifaceted treatment plans among a team of hospital- and community-based providers and collects data to support treatment planning</p> <p>5.2/ABC Supervises and serves as a role model for trainees and staff</p>

Supplementary File 1

MK1—Clinical neuroscience of emergency psychiatry				
A. Describe the neuroscientific basis of common emergency psychopathology including agitation and substance use disorders				
B. Describe the neuropharmacology of substances of abuse and medication treatments				
C. Understand potential contributions of development and interruptions thereof to acute behavioral emergencies				
Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Level 4	Level 5
<p>1.1/AB Demonstrates at least limited knowledge regarding science and pharmacology relevant to emergency psychiatry</p> <p>1.2/AB Appreciates the potential role substance use and withdrawal might play in psychiatric emergencies</p> <p>1.3/C Applies knowledge of development in approaching child/adolescent psychiatric emergencies</p>	<p>2.1/ABC Demonstrates basic knowledge regarding science and pharmacology relevant to emergency psychiatry and applies this knowledge in assessment and treatment planning</p>	<p>3.1/ABC Demonstrates comprehensive knowledge regarding science and pharmacology relevant to emergency psychiatry and applies this knowledge in more complex patients with co-morbid illness</p> <p>3.2/AC Approaches case formulation with a trauma-informed attitude that reflects an understanding of the lasting effects trauma may have on behavior</p>	<p>4.1/ABC Demonstrates comprehensive knowledge regarding science and pharmacology relevant to emergency psychiatry and applies this knowledge in patients with rare or highly complex illnesses</p> <p>4.2/ABC Teaches and demonstrates application of this knowledge to members of a multidisciplinary team</p>	<p>5.1/ABC Develops, synthesizes, or presents new knowledge regarding treatment and pathology relevant to emergency psychiatry</p>

Supplementary File 1

MK2—Epidemiology of emergency psychiatry				
A. Describe demographic, socioeconomic, and clinical risk factors for suicide, violence, and healthcare utilization				
B. Apply evidence-based screening and assessment tools in managing risk and clinical presentations in the emergency department				
C. Describe the evidence base for medication, psychotherapeutic, and psychosocial interventions in emergency psychiatry				
Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Level 4	Level 5
1.1/ABC Demonstrates limited knowledge of epidemiology relevant to emergency psychiatry 1.2/C Demonstrates understanding of psychotropic selection based on current practice guidelines	2.1/ABC Demonstrates basic knowledge of epidemiology relevant to emergency psychiatry and applies this knowledge in assessment and treatment planning	3.1/ABC Demonstrates comprehensive knowledge regarding epidemiology relevant to emergency psychiatry and applies this knowledge in more complex patients with co-morbid illness 3.2/AB Understands the role of neuroimaging, neuropsychological and other testing in psychiatric emergency presentations	4.1/ABC Demonstrates comprehensive knowledge regarding epidemiology relevant to emergency psychiatry and applies this knowledge in patients with rare or highly complex illnesses 4.2/ABC Teaches and demonstrates application of this knowledge to members of a multidisciplinary team	5.1/ABC Develops, synthesizes, or presents new knowledge regarding epidemiology relevant to emergency psychiatry 5.2/BC Implements innovative programs that translate scientific findings into clinical practice

Supplementary File 1

SBP1—Patient safety and the health care team				
A. Lead a multidisciplinary team in avoiding medical errors				
B. Practice with consideration of the service’s performance metrics				
C. Apply techniques for assessing and improving the quality of care in the psychiatric emergency service				
Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Level 4	Level 5
<p>1.1/AC Describes common systematic causes of medical errors</p> <p>1.2/B Describes metrics relevant to patient safety and clinical performance</p> <p>1.3/ABC Follows regulatory requirements related to reporting and prescribing</p>	<p>2.1/AC Describes systems that are in place to reduce systematic errors</p> <p>2.2/ABC Discusses opportunities to improve patient safety and outcomes</p>	<p>3.1/A Uses safety and reporting procedures</p> <p>3.2/ABC Communicates effectively with team members around safety and performance concerns</p> <p>3.3/C Describes approaches for assessing and improving quality of care</p>	<p>4.1/ABC Contributes to a project that enhances patient safety and clinical care</p> <p>4.2/AB Considers patient safety and performance metrics while making clinical decisions as leader of a multidisciplinary team</p> <p>4.3/C Develops content for and facilitates presentations or interventions focused on systems-based errors in patient care</p>	<p>5ABC Designs and implements a project or curriculum to enhance patient safety or improve operational performance</p> <p>5.2/ABC Leads a multidisciplinary team in addressing patient safety concerns</p>

Supplementary File 1

SBP2—Resource management				
A. Consider the cost of care in practicing emergency psychiatry				
B. Utilize alternative less costly treatment alternatives when appropriate				
C. Describe the role of healthcare payers in controlling costs and improving outcomes				
Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Level 4	Level 5
1.1/AC Describes existing disparities in health care	2.1/ABC Coordinates with payers in accessing less costly treatment alternatives	3.1/ABC Develops treatment plans that consider patients' individual and community limitations in accessing care	4.1/ABC Develops treatment plans that actively decrease costs for patients (eg, providing brief treatment in the emergency department in order to access a lower level of care)	5.1/ABC Designs and implements a project or curriculum to enhance operational efficiency
1.2/B Knows the relative cost of recommended treatments	2.2/B Integrates options for averting emergency department visits into treatment planning (eg, describing community-based services)	3.2/B Counsels patients on financial cost when developing treatment plans	4.2/C Takes advantage of regulatory and financial pressures to help patients access treatment (eg, connects patients with insurance-based care navigators)	5.2/C Advocates for additional resources relevant to improved patient safety and care
	2.3/C Advocates for patients in navigating financial matters relevant to treatment recommendations	3.3/B Practices effectively in less costly treatment settings (eg, crisis phone counseling) under indirect supervision with direct supervision available		

Supplementary File 1

SBP3—Community-based collaboration w/ general psychiatrists, non-psychiatric medical providers, and non-medical systems				
A. Consult and collaborate with external clinical providers in the management of emergent psychiatric presentations				
B. Consult to non-clinical community partners on emergency psychiatric presentations (eg, police, schools)				
C. Understand outside resources available to complement treatment planning				
Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Level 4	Level 5
1.1/ABC Describes local health care delivery systems and partners	2.1/ABC Coordinates with external clinical and community partners in developing assessments and treatment plans	3.1/ABC Provides feedback to external clinical and community partners on improving the care of an individual patient (eg, sharing a treatment plan should psychiatric symptoms decompensate)	4.1/ABC Leads a multidisciplinary team in coordinating with an external network of providers	5.1/ABC Develops new clinical programs that enhance communication and coordination among multiple clinical or social service entities
1.2/A Clarifies the consultation question, demonstrating clear understanding of the consultant’s role/limits	2.2/C Incorporates disorder-specific support and advocacy groups in clinical care	3.2/ABC Uses principles of evidence-based practice and patient-centered care in management of chronically ill patients	4.2/AB Provides expert consultation on complex cases to outside partners under indirect supervision	5.2/ABC Creates new partnerships that enhance the treatment of patients presenting to the emergency department (eg, a new process to facilitate referrals)
1.3/ABC Describes differences in providing consultation to a system/team versus to an individual patient	2.3/ABC Appropriately refers to rehabilitation and recovery programs			

Supplementary File 1

PBLI1—Development of lifelong learning practices and application of evidence-based care				
A. Engage in continual self-assessment and self-directed learning				
B. Integrate evidence-based resources and scientific literature into bedside clinical care				
C. Utilize supervision and consultation when appropriate				
Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Level 4	Level 5
1.1/AC Regularly seeks and incorporates feedback to improve performance	2.1/AB Demonstrates a balanced and accurate self-assessment of competence in clinical practice and team leadership	3.1/AC Reflects on opportunities to improve patient care through personal clinical experiences	4.1/AB Participates in teaching activities that improve the knowledge of the team in providing care	5.1/ABC Supervises and serves as a role model to trainees and staff in incorporating gathered evidence into clinical workflow
1.2/B Describes available evidence-based information tools to inform care	2.2/AB Selects an appropriate evidence-based information tool to meet learning goals	3.2/B Efficiently and effectively uses medical literature to improve the care of patients	4.2/BC Consistently and independently integrates contemporary literature and evidence into clinical decision-making	5.2/B Develops new educational and training curricula teaching appraisal of clinical evidence

Supplementary File 1

PBLI2—Practice-based quality improvement				
A. Apply formal teaching in quality improvement and program evaluation				
B. Lead a multidisciplinary team in achieving shared performance metrics				
Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Level 4	Level 5
1.1/AB Describes performance metrics in context of the team’s work 1.2/A Participates in formal training on quality improvement	2.1/AB Identifies opportunities to improve performance and safety on a multidisciplinary team 2.2/B Identifies common responses of team and individuals to changes in clinical operations and discusses strategies for managing these	3.1/AB Interprets the importance of quality improvement and program evaluation to a clinical team 3.2/AB Describes core concepts of QI methodologies, evaluation and implementation of clinical QI projects	4.1/AB Contributes to a project that uses knowledge of quality improvement processes to enhance safety and/or performance of the unit 4.2/B Demonstrates unit-based leadership in implementing performance improvement activities	5.1/AB Designs original quality improvement and program evaluation activities to enhance patient safety and unit performance

Supplementary File 1

PBLI3—Clinical teaching				
A. Effectively teach all members of a multidisciplinary team (eg, students, nurses, social workers, clerks, residents)				
B. Demonstrate effective teaching in bedside, classroom, and community settings				
Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Level 4	Level 5
<p>1.1/AB Recognizes the physician as teacher and assumes a teaching role among clinical trainees and staff</p> <p>1.2/B Appreciates the rich and unique teaching environment provided by the emergency psychiatric service</p>	<p>2.1/AB Provides effective feedback to trainees and staff both at the bedside and through cumulative evaluations</p> <p>2.2/AB Participates in didactic presentations to trainees and staff</p> <p>2.3/AB Receives positive evaluations on teaching</p>	<p>3.1/AB Tailors teaching to a level appropriate for the trainee</p> <p>3.2/AB Effectively incorporates feedback on teaching to improve teaching methods and approaches</p>	<p>4.1/AB Develops and delivers consistently effective teaching presentations</p> <p>4.2/AB Supervises midlevel clinicians and staff in the course of routine clinical care</p>	<p>5.1/AB Is recognized as an exceptional educator of colleagues and staff</p> <p>5.2/AB Educates the broader professional community and/or public</p> <p>5.3/AB Develops novel training curricula</p>

Supplementary File 1

PROF1—Compassion, integrity, and respect				
A. Demonstrate compassion and empathy with patients and colleagues				
B. Practice and lead ethically with humility and a sense of duty towards others				
C. Maintain professional boundaries				
Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Level 4	Level 5
<p>1.1/A Demonstrates capacity for self-reflection, empathy, openness to different beliefs, and respect for diversity</p> <p>1.2/BC Recognizes ethical conflicts in practice and seeks supervision to manage them</p>	<p>2.1/AB Routinely displays empathy, compassion, and sensitivity with patients and colleagues</p> <p>2.2/BC Manages ethical conflicts that arise in clinical practices and discusses those conflicts among the team</p> <p>2.3/AB Recognizes individual and family values and is able to appreciate the potential impact on patient care</p>	<p>3.1/A Facilitates positive communication among the team and patients</p> <p>3.2/BC Manages professional conflicts in the workplace without compromising one’s integrity or ability to lead</p>	<p>4.1/ABC Consistently displays compassion, integrity, and sensitivity even under high pressure scenarios</p> <p>4.2/ABC Recognizes personal limitations and maintains integrity while adapting the approach to patient care</p>	<p>5.1/ABC Serves as a role model among trainees, staff, and colleagues in managing difficult ethical and professional situations</p> <p>5.2/B Identifies emerging ethical issues in the subspecialty and applies novel interventions</p>

Supplementary File 1

PROF2—Accountability to one’s self, patients, colleagues, and profession				
A. Recognize and mitigate burnout				
B. Contribute to one’s professional community				
C. Perform duties with integrity and respect				
Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Level 4	Level 5
<p>1.1/A Notifies colleagues and enlists appropriate coverage for responsibilities when unable to complete</p> <p>1.2/BC Follows institutional policies for physician conduct and responsibility</p>	<p>2.1/AC Pro-actively identifies situations in which personal health or responsibilities will compromise availability to the team</p> <p>2.2/B Recognizes the importance of participating in one’s professional community</p>	<p>3.1/A Demonstrates healthy and responsible work style (eg, use of time off)</p> <p>3.2/BC Displays professionalism in work and collaborations</p> <p>3.3/B Maintains skills including meeting requirements for ongoing education</p>	<p>4.1/A Helps colleagues recognize and mitigate burnout</p> <p>4.2/AB Effectively prioritizes and balances conflicting interests to one’s self, family, patients, and others</p> <p>4.3/C Displays increasing autonomy and leadership in taking responsibility for ensuring patients receive the best possible care</p>	<p>5.1/A Participates in organizations that address physician wellness</p> <p>5.2/ABC Serves as a role model for trainees and staff in demonstrating accountability to patients and service</p> <p>5.3/B Assumes leadership roles in professional organizations</p>

Supplementary File 1

ICS1—Relationship development and conflict management				
A. Manage conflict among patients, families, colleagues, and the health care team				
B. Maintain effective and functioning relationships among patients, families, colleagues, and the health care team even in high stress circumstances				
Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Level 4	Level 5
<p>1.1/AB Develops therapeutic or professional relationships with patients and co-workers respectively</p> <p>1.2/B Recognizes communication conflicts among patients and staff</p> <p>1.3/A Independently provides verbal de-escalation</p>	<p>2.1/A Develops therapeutic relations with patients that are respectful of personal and cultural differences</p> <p>2.2/AB Develops working relationship among clinicians of different backgrounds and across systems of care</p> <p>2.3/A Negotiates and manages challenging patient/family-related conflicts</p>	<p>3.1/A Recognizes conflict induced by challenging patient care scenarios</p> <p>3.2/AB Sustains working relationships in the face of conflict or differences of opinion</p>	<p>4.1/AB Manages conflicts among the team in a way that respects others' opinions and values</p> <p>4.2/B Considers the individual backgrounds of team members when managing conflict under complex or challenging scenarios</p>	<p>5.1/AB Mentors others in leadership, communication skills, and conflict management</p> <p>5.2/AB Develops scholarship related to teamwork and conflict management</p>

Supplementary File 1

ICS2—Information sharing and record keeping				
A. Maintain accurate documentation				
B. Communicate effectively with colleagues and patients				
C. Understanding of potential barriers to and importance of professional, effective communication				
Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Level 4	Level 5
<p>1.1/ABC Documents transitions of care and completes documentation in a timely fashion consistent with hospital policy</p> <p>1.2/AB Organizes written and oral information effectively</p> <p>1.3/BC Uses social media appropriately and professionally</p>	<p>2.1/A Documents interaction with external providers</p> <p>2.2/BC Demonstrates communication strategies to facilitate patients’ understanding of clinical information (eg, use of interpreters, use of technology, easy-to-use language)</p> <p>2.3/BC Respects patient confidentiality</p>	<p>3.1/AB Demonstrates oral and written communication that is not only accurate but also concise and efficient</p> <p>3.2/BC Consistently engages patients and families in shared decision making</p>	<p>4.1/AB Demonstrates oral and written communication that is accurate and efficient even with challenging case presentations</p> <p>4.2/A Documents with consideration of regulatory and billing requirements</p> <p>4.3/BC Uses discretion and judgment in documenting sensitive material</p>	<p>5.1/ABC Develops new modes of system organization that facilitate communication with patients and among colleagues</p>